

Magritek Spinsolve NMR

This guide explains how to add Magritek NMR to the Chemotion ELN device pool. The protocol enables remote access to the PC running Spinsolve and the transfer of experiment data to the Chemotion ELN's inbox. Both these can be set up separately, with neither relying on the other. The data transfer is configured for experiments conducted directly in Spinsolve.

Considering all the [general preparation aspects](#), this procedure has been conducted on the following system configurations. However, it is likely to work on systems with different software versions as well.

Specifications of the device's PC

- Operating system: Windows 10
- Software Name: Spinsolve (Version: 2.0.1)
- Connected to Internet/Intranet: Yes
- Data files generated: 1D file (.1d)
- Static IP address has been configured

Objectives

- Remote Device Control
- Data transfer to Chemotion ELN inbox

Configurations

Remote Device Control

General guidelines regarding the configurations of remote device control can be found [here](#).

Data transfer

Data will automatically be transferred to the Chemotion ELN once the data has been saved locally on the computer. The user only needs to make sure to name the output file according to the [naming convention](#) before saving it to the local machine.

Configurations in NMR PC

The NMR's PC and the Chemotion ELN both need access to a common network storage location. This can be set up on a third-party storage (a NAS server, shared storage of another PC, etc) or it can be set up locally on the NMR PC.

In this case, the LSDF storage service from KIT has been used which has been later on mounted in the NMR's PC as a network drive under Netzwerkadressen i.e. Network Address. For this guide, the LSDF folder was mounted as a network drive of the NMR PC using the [SMB/CIFS on Windows](#) configurations.

Configurations in Spinsolve

We can see that the data is stored both locally and on a remote server when we look at Spinsolve's data storage options. Now as for the remote backup storage location, the network drive we created will be used. The Chemotion ELN also has access to this storage location. The experiment data file will be automatically saved at this location besides the local drive and Chemotion ELN will be able to retrieve and transfer it to the appropriate user's inbox.

The screenshot shows the Spinsolve 2.0.1 software interface. The top navigation bar includes MENU, SYSTEM, Prefs, SETUP, INTERFACE, and HISTORY. The main content area is titled 'GLOBAL DATA STORAGE' and contains the following settings:

- SAVE DURING EXPERIMENT: SAVE EVERY: 1 SCANS
- DATA PATH: E:\DATA (with a folder icon)
- EXAMPLE: E:\DATA\BT008-CRUDE-DMDO_11
- BACKUP DATA PATH: Z:\ELN (with a folder icon)
- LEGEND:
 - SELECT FOLDER FOR BASE PATH (green square icon)
 - CHOOSE BETWEEN SUBFOLDER (/) OR NAME_EXTENSION (-) (dropdown arrow icon)
 - CHOOSE VARIABLE (dropdown arrow icon)
 - ADD ADDITIONAL VARIABLE (+ icon)
 - REMOVE VARIABLE (x icon)
 - MOVE VARIABLE LEFT (left arrow icon)
 - MOVE VARIABLE RIGHT (right arrow icon)
- BACKUP ERROR MESSAGE: DISPLAY ERROR MESSAGE WHEN BACKUP FAILED
- SAVE JCAMP-DX OUTPUT:
- SAVE 1D SPECTRUM CSV:
- RMX SAVE EACH PROTOCOL:

On the left side, there is a 'SETUP' menu with the following options (all collapsed): PDF REPORT SETTINGS, QNMR SETTINGS, EMAIL SETTINGS, LICENSES, HARDWARE, DATA PROCESSING, REMOTE CONTROL, SAMPLE CHANGER, and PUMP.

To make sure that Chemotion ELN can transfer it to the appropriate user's inbox, we have to make sure the samples are named following the [naming convention](#).

Here the naming of the sample has started with the name abbreviation (Kürzel) of a certain user to whom the experiment data file will be sent.

SPINSOLVE 2.0.1

MENU ^1H PROTON PROTON+ PROTON FDEC PRESAT PRESAT MULTI PARAMAG

Spinsolve

1D PROTON

START

SAMPLE X

SOLVENT X

CUSTOM X

QUICKSCAN: 10 SECONDS

STANDARDSCAN: 1 MINUTE

POWERSCAN: 10 MINUTES

QUANTITY	85.35
QUANTITY VS REFERENCE	5.77

Now data experiment data will be transferred to the network storage location so that the data collector of Chemotion ELN can retrieve it from there.

Configurations in Chemotion ELN

The Chemotion ELN's data collector has to be configured to collect data from the NMR from the network location.

As for the file collector mechanism, there are two options.

- Collecting attachment files from emails
- Collecting files or folders from local drives or over SCP

Here in this guide, we have used the second mechanism where the files are collected from remote storage locations and are distributed to specific users based on the file-name matching the name abbreviation of the user. You can find details [here](#).